

CONCRETE BLOCKS SURVEY FORM

Dear respondent,

I am **Masaba Emmison Eric**, pursuing a Master of Science in Structural Engineering (GMES). I am carrying out research titled "**COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF PLASTIC BOTTLE BRICK MASONRY LOAD BEARING WALLS**", which involves **comparison of the proposed Plastic Bottle Block to the existing Hollow & Solid concrete blocks**.

This tool aims at establishing baseline data for **methods used in production of hollow and solid concrete blocks**. The information and data obtained in the survey will be used for conducting relevant analysis on aggregate basis for the purpose of the survey and **SHALL BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL**.

This survey form has only Eight (8) questions, it will take very little of your time

** Indicates required question*

1. Block description

This section gives an understanding of the composition of a concrete block.

1. 1.1 What type of blocks do you make? *

Mark only one oval.

- Hollow blocks only
- Solid blocks only
- Both hollow and solid blocks

2. 1.2 What materials are used to manufacture your blocks? *

(You can select more than one option)

Check all that apply.

- Cement
- Sand
- Stone dust
- Aggregates/stones
- Other: _____

3. 1.3 What mixing ratio do you use for making your blocks? *

4. 1.4 How do you measure the quantities for materials used to make the blocks? *

Mark only one oval.

- Batching boxes
- Bags of cement and wheel barrows
- Weighed proportions
- Other: _____

2. Processing of blocks

This section gives an understanding of the processes in making blocks.

5. 2.1 What concrete block curing methods do you use? *

Check all that apply.

- Covering
- Spraying with water
- Ponding/immersion in water
- None of the above
- Other: _____

6. **2.2 What is the minimum curing time for your blocks? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 7 days
- 2 weeks
- 3 weeks
- 4 weeks or longer

7. **2.3 Do you have any further advice/information you would like to share about concrete blocks?**

The End

Thank you for your participation in this study, I am really grateful.

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